

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ЕФЕКТИВНІСТЬ ТА ТРАНСПАРЕНТНІСТЬ АУДИТУ В ДЕРЖАВНОМУ СЕКТОРІ: АНАЛІЗ, ВИКЛИКИ ТА ПЕРСПЕКТИВИ

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AUDIT EFFICIENCY AND TRANSPARENCY IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR: ANALYSIS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

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АННОТАЦІЯ

В сучасних умовах глобальних трансформацій та стрімкого розвитку суспільства ефективне управління фінансовими ресурсами державного сектору стає ключовим аспектом забезпечення стабільності та розвитку країни. Однією з найважливіших складових цього процесу є аудит, який визначається не лише як інструмент перевірки відповідності фінансових операцій встановленим стандартам, але й як ключовий механізм забезпечення транспарентності та ефективності управління державними ресурсами.

Ця наукова стаття спрямована на глибокий аналіз ефективності та транспарентності аудиторських процесів в державному секторі. З урахуванням викликів, які стоять перед сучасними урядовими структурами, дослідження має на меті визначення ключових аспектів, які впливають на результативність аудиторської діяльності, а також розгляд можливих перспектив для підвищення якості та ефективності цього процесу в контексті публічного управління.

Надзвичайна важливість аудиту в державному секторі полягає в його здатності не лише виявляти можливі фінансові ризики та невідповідності, але й створювати умови для покращення ефективності роботи органів влади.

ABSTRACT

In today's conditions of global transformations and rapid development of society, the effective management of public sector financial resources becomes a key aspect of ensuring the country's stability and development. One of the most important components of this process is the audit, which is defined not only as a tool for checking compliance of financial operations with established standards, but also as a key mechanism for ensuring transparency and efficiency of state resource management.

This scientific article is aimed at an in-depth analysis of the effectiveness and transparency of audit processes in the public sector. Taking into account the challenges facing modern government structures, the research aims to identify key aspects that affect the effectiveness of audit activity, as well as consider possible prospects for improving the quality and efficiency of this process in the context of public administration.

The extraordinary importance of audit in the public sector lies in its ability not only to identify possible financial risks and inconsistencies, but also to create conditions for improving the efficiency of the authorities.

Ключові слова: ефективність, аудит, виклики, трансформації, державне управління, стандартизація.
Keywords: efficiency, audit, challenges, transformations, public administration, standardization.

Statement of the problem. Against the background of modern challenges and transformations of public administration, where the amount of financial resources is growing rapidly and the scope of public functions is expanding, the efficiency and transparency of audit processes in the public sector are of crucial importance for ensuring sustainable development and citizens' trust in government administration [1].

Despite the prominence of the importance of audit, there are significant problems and challenges that make it difficult to conduct an effective and transparent audit in the public sector.

The insufficient level of coordination between audit bodies, the ambiguity of audit methodologies and the insufficient implementation of modern technologies in conducting audit processes - all this calls into question the effectiveness and objectivity of audits in state institutions.

This article is aimed at an in-depth analysis of these problems, as well as the identification of key factors that affect the effectiveness and transparency of audit processes in the public sector. Through a careful study of these aspects, the article aims to offer specific

recommendations for improving the quality and effectiveness of auditing activities, thus contributing to the improvement of managerial efficiency and ensuring the stable development of the state [5].

Analysis of recent research and publications.

The latest scientific research and publications show a great interest in the management of financial resources and ensuring openness in the activities of state institutions. Several key directions and trends are highlighted, which should be taken into account in the context of consideration of this issue.

1. Methodologies and Standards. Modern studies emphasize the importance of developing and unifying audit methodologies in the public sector. Attempts to standardize processes allow not only to improve the quality of audit procedures, but also to create a basis for comparing results and objectively evaluating efficiency.

2. Use of Technologies. Recent studies emphasize the role of modern technologies, such as artificial intelligence, blockchain and data analytics, in improving the transparency and speed of audit processes. The implementation of these technologies can significantly facilitate the collection and analysis of information, which is critical in the public sector.

3. Role of Audit Bodies. The need to increase the role of audit bodies in controlling costs and the effectiveness of management decisions is noted. The dynamics of the development of the auditing profession and its adaptation to modern requirements and technological changes are analyzed.

4. Issues of Trust and Openness. Great emphasis is placed on the importance of increasing public confidence in audit processes in the public sector. Practices for ensuring the openness and availability of audit results for a wide audience are considered [2].

These recent studies provide the basis for further analysis and identification of strategies to overcome the challenges facing public sector auditing and to identify prospects for improving efficiency and transparency in this area.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. In the context of the general problem of audit efficiency and transparency in the public sector, a number of aspects remain unresolved or require additional clarification and research. Some of them act as key sub-problems that can determine the overall success of audit activity and affect the level of efficiency of financial resources management in the public sector [4-8]:

1. Methodological disagreement. The issue of methodological differences between auditing approaches in different spheres of public administration remains open. Is there a need to standardize audit methods for different types of public institutions?

2. Challenges of ensuring objectivity. The problem of ensuring the objectivity and dispassion of audit processes, especially when interacting with government structures. How can the independence of auditors be guaranteed and the possibility of a conflict of interest excluded?

3. Effectiveness of the audit system. Uncertainty about how effectively public sector audit institutions

perform their functions. What factors affect their effectiveness, and how can this be measured and evaluated?

4. Auditing culture and qualifications. Consideration of issues related to the development of audit culture and improvement of qualifications of audit personnel in the public sector.

How can you ensure a high level of professional training and ethics among auditors? These unresolved aspects become key in the context of the development of proposals and recommendations aimed at improving the quality and effectiveness of auditing activities in the public sector and formulating prospects for the development of this area.

The study is aimed at determining the key aspects that affect the effectiveness of audit activity in the public sector and at identifying possible ways to solve them. The specific steps of the research goal include: analysis of the current state of audit activity in the public sector; determination of influencing factors on audit efficiency and transparency; systematization of challenges and problems preventing the achievement of a high level of efficiency in audit processes in the public sector; consideration of prospects for the development of audit in the public sector; formulation of specific recommendations and strategies aimed at improving the efficiency and transparency of auditing in the public sector. The ultimate goal of the steps is to promote the development of sustainable and effective management of public finances in modern conditions.

The aim of the research. The purpose of this scientific article is an in-depth analysis and assessment of the effectiveness and transparency of audit in the public sector, as well as the identification of challenges that question its operational effectiveness. The study is aimed at determining the key aspects that affect the effectiveness of audit activity in the public sector and at identifying possible ways to solve them.

Specific steps of the research objective include [3]:

1. Analysis of the current state. Conduct a comprehensive analysis of the current state of audit activity in the public sector, identify its main advantages and disadvantages.

2. Determination of influencing factors. To determine the key factors affecting the effectiveness and transparency of the audit in the conditions of state administration, taking into account the specifics of the work of audit bodies and their relationship with government structures.

3. Identification of challenges and problems. To reveal and systematize challenges and problems that prevent the achievement of a high level of efficiency in audit processes in the public sector.

4. Consideration of development prospects. To determine possible prospects for the development of audit in the public sector, in particular, through the introduction of new technologies, improvement of personnel qualifications and improvement of the legislative framework.

5. Formulation of recommendations. Based on the obtained results, formulate specific recommendations and strategies aimed at improving the efficiency and transparency of audits in the public sector.

The purpose of this study is to contribute to the improvement of the audit system of public administration, to ensure its high efficiency and to promote the development of sustainable and effective financial management in modern conditions.

Presentation of the main material. To date, state institutions actively use audit mechanisms to check compliance of financial transactions with established standards. However, despite some improvements, there are challenges that prevent the achievement of full efficiency.

1. Analysis of the Current State of Auditing in the Public Sector.

1.1 Level of Transparency. Starting with the analysis of the current state, the level of transparency in audit processes of the public sector should be noted. Careful research shows that, despite some improvements, there are challenges in ensuring the openness and availability of information necessary for an effective audit.

The main challenges, in our opinion, are related to the organizational structure of audit in the public sector. If we are talking about developing countries, then there is actually no clear structure, instead, state financial control (audit), aimed at identifying the compliance of economic facts and documents with established standards, is of dominant importance. There is no question of a public audit as such, since retrospective assessment is decisive. Countries with a developed economy strive to build a comprehensive public sector audit system, in which the complementary components are a compliance audit, a performance audit, and a financial audit. At the same time, the main system-forming element should be the efficiency audit, which corresponds to the concept of the budget process based on the program-target method. Accordingly, the separation of types of thematic audit (for example, judicial audit and audit of administrative responsibility) as separate subsystems of public audit, which is proposed by some scientific schools [9, p. 343], has no scientific basis.

The problem of transparency of audit processes is directly related to this problem. Ensuring access to information and audit results for a wide audience remains a challenge that requires further improvement. Compliance audits and financial audits are traditionally less open to audits and publicizing the results. The objective limitation here is the closure of factual audit sources, which contain a significant share of confidential information. Its disclosure is potentially unfavorable for public sector entities. At the same time, the results of the audit of financial reporting and financial management (as forms of financial audit) are an object of wide public interest and certify compliance with regulatory requirements (standards). Under such conditions, the primary task is to find a balance between the level of transparency of the audit and the degree of threat to the economic security of the subjects of control. On the other hand, the effectiveness audit is a priori characterized by publicity, because its results are a comprehensive assessment of the activities of state bodies and institutions and the basis for adjusting budget flows.

1.2 Differences in Methodologies. Questions arise regarding differences in methodological approaches

between audit bodies. Attempts at unification may be key to ensuring objectivity and comparability of results.

Currently, we proceed from the distinction of two basic groups of public audit subjects: users of audit results and subjects responsible for its conduct (auditors, public organizations, consulting firms, and the like). The definition of research methodology, technology and tools is especially important for the subjects of the second group. Specific audit techniques (methods) may vary depending on the subject area of the audit, controlled entities and other factors, but are always limited to the methods of actual (organoleptic) and documentary (including computational and analytical) control. In fact, the methodological toolkit of public audit as a whole corresponds to the concept of obtaining audit evidence according to ISA 500 "Audit evidence" (documentary control by inspection, confirmation requests, counting, analytical procedures and actual control by observation).

Therefore, we believe that despite the sectoral differences, it is advisable to standardize the development of the audit methodology based on the SMART methodology (Specific – Measurable – Achievable – Realistic – Timed), which will determine the effectiveness of audit activities.

2. Determination of Influence Factors:

2.1 Role of Technologies. Detailed analysis of the role of technology, in particular artificial intelligence and blockchain, in audit processes. Implementation of these innovations can improve the accuracy, efficiency and objectivity of audit activities.

Today, blockchain has become a fundamental tool in all industries that rely on transactions, as it simplifies user personalization, offers robust security measures, and increases privacy and data protection. Moreover, the added value of this database tool is so great that, according to PwC forecasts, it will add \$1.76 trillion to the global economy by 2030 [11]. The importance of blockchain technologies in auditing is evidenced by the fact that the largest auditing companies (PwC, Deloitte, Ernst & Young, KPMG) are actively offering products based on them today. They provide cost savings for obtaining information, a significant increase in the efficiency of management decision-making and the quality of corporate transactions. Despite this, an objective limitation for the use of these technologies in the public sector should be the search for a balance between the openness of information (financial transparency) provided by blockchain technology and the potentially negative impact of the dissemination of confidential data.

2.2 Coordination and Cooperation. Identification of problems related to insufficient coordination and cooperation between audit bodies and other branches of state administration indicates the need to ensure effective coordination and cooperation between them and requires systemic solutions. On the one hand, organizational structures and civil servants performing public audits must be independent from other branches of state administration in the selection of audit procedures and decision-making. At the same time, it is necessary to ensure their accountability and responsibility for conducting the audit, the reliability of its results and public

consequences. On the other hand, the efficiency of the audit increases as a result of the coordinated cooperation of the participants of the public audit (understanding of the information system, saving time for searching for information, obtaining audit evidence, etc.). In order to avoid the duplication of functions and powers of public audit subjects, which does not contribute to increasing its efficiency, it is appropriate to coordinate regulatory acts on public audit procedures at the institutional level; determine the procedure for coordinating actions regarding planning, organization and direct implementation of the audit; establish the procedure for exchanging information that is necessary for conducting an audit and certifying its results. Business practice confirms that the use of uniform, clear audit rules in the

public sector contributes to a more complete coverage of the subject area of the audit and an increase in the quality of the audit.

3. Identification of Challenges and Problems:

3.1 Transparency and Trust. Consideration of the problem of lack of public confidence and trust in audit results and possible ways to increase transparency.

The reliability of audit results objectively affects the level of public trust. The importance of increasing transparency to ensure trust is becoming apparent. A vivid example of such a relationship is the Ukrainian experience of closing public access to information on procurement by state customers in connection with the armed invasion of Russia on the territory of Ukraine in February 2022 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Dynamics of the number of announced public procurements in Ukraine from January to August [4, p. 7]

The decrease in transparency of the system, which became fully operational only on January 1, 2021, led to large-scale violations and abuses in the public sector. Only according to the data of the state monitoring of public sector purchases for 2022, more than 66% of violations were detected. Many high-profile facts were also revealed as a result of a public audit from the public. At the same time, the level of public trust in the published audit results is consistently high.

3.2 Effectiveness of Audit Bodies. Determination of factors affecting the effectiveness of audit bodies. These are, for example, insufficient budget, low level of personnel qualification, limited time and other resources, etc., which complicate the work of audit bodies and reduce their effectiveness.

The factor of alternative costs for conducting a public audit claims to be deeply studied in connection with the availability of alternative options when choosing a part. Incorrect choice of topics, tasks, and control methods by subjects of a public audit can cause loss or irrational spending of public resources. Accordingly, the effectiveness of audit bodies will increase only if opportunity costs are minimized.

4. Consideration of Development Prospects:

4.1 Innovative Approaches. The introduction of innovative technologies and methods can become the key to increasing the effectiveness of the audit and improving its transparency.

In this context, first of all, it is worth considering digital audit and the latest data analysis tools, which require a review of the functions of auditors in response

to the digital transformation of public and private sector companies. Modern Core GAM and Digital GAM methodologies are successfully applied by the largest auditing companies. They require modern auditors to be proficient with analytical tools and allow them to process large amounts of Helix clients' financial information. At the same time, they contribute to the reduction of the amount of technical work and the use of freed time for the qualitative application of analytical procedures. Such a vector of development leads to a closer relationship and transparency and, as a result, greater trust of interested parties. Despite this, it is worth considering and minimizing the risks associated with digital auditing (ensuring data confidentiality and using large data sets).

4.2 Improvement of Qualifications and Culture. Improving the qualifications of audit staff and developing a high professional culture can contribute to the achievement of high standards of activity in this area.

The International Code of Ethics of Professional Accountants enshrines a set of basic standards for accountants and auditors: performing work with a high level of professionalism, achieving the best results in their activities and, in general, satisfying public interests. That is, there is a direct connection between the professionalism of auditors and the reliability of audit results, which is manifested by the degree of trust of the public and other interested parties in the results of audits in the public sector. Therefore, continuous professional development and strict adherence to the princi-

ples of professional ethics (integrity, objectivity, professional competence and due diligence, confidentiality, professional conduct, technical standards) are the guarantee of well-founded public trust.

5. Formulation of Recommendations:

5.1 Improvement Tools. With the challenges mentioned above, taking into account the prospects, it is possible to formulate a number of recommendations. Implementation of systematic changes in the methodology, active use of the latest technologies and continuous improvement of professional competences are only some of the ways to achieve high efficiency and transparency of auditing in the public sector. We emphasize that the listed recommendations are based on the concept of a risk-oriented approach and ensure the organization of audits in the public sector taking into account specific risk events, which significantly reduces the costs of its maintenance and increases the efficiency of the system.

This analytical presentation serves as a basis for further discussions and formulation of conclusions, which are aimed at determining ways to improve the efficiency and transparency of audit in the public sector.

Conclusions. Auditing in the public sector requires constant improvement and adaptation to new realities. Overcoming the identified challenges will require joint efforts of government structures, auditing bodies and the public. Only under the condition of a systematic approach and the introduction of innovations, it is possible to ensure high quality and efficiency of audit processes in the public sector, which meets the requirements of the modern world.

In the context of our study of audit effectiveness and transparency in the public sector, we can formulate key conclusions that relate to the current state, identified challenges and prospects for further development of this important area of management.

1. Current State and Its Assessment. The analysis showed that at the current stage, the public sector actively uses audit as a tool for control and ensuring openness. However, the level of transparency and methodological differences remain important issues that need attention.

2. Challenges and Problems. Identified challenges, such as insufficient coordination between audit bodies, low level of transparency and non-uniformity of methodologies, turned out to be key limiting factors for achieving maximum effectiveness of audit processes.

3. Development prospects. Against the background of identified challenges, it is important to consider development prospects. Implementation of innovative technologies, standardization of methodologies and improvement of staff qualifications are key directions for further improvement of audit.

4. Importance of Transparency and Trust. Ensuring a high level of transparency and trust becomes critical to improving audit effectiveness. Transparency not only strengthens the internal legitimacy of processes, but also promotes active public participation in the control of the financial sphere.

5. Necessity of an Integrated Approach. The conclusions of our research confirm that solving the identified problems requires a comprehensive and integrated approach. The joint efforts of government structures, audit bodies, and the public are important to achieve high standards of financial management in the public sector.

6. Favorable Development Prospects. Despite the challenges highlighted in the research, favorable prospects for the development of audit in the public sector include the introduction of innovations, the creation of a unified methodological platform, and an increase in the level of professional training.

7. Key Areas of Action. Based on the findings, key areas of action are defined, such as development of standards, increased funding of audit bodies, and implementation of effective innovations.

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